

An ecological study of allergy epidemiology in Spain: a 25-year time-series research: Quantitative statistics supporting the allergy growth

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Abstract

Background: Allergic illnesses are among the most common causes of chronic pathology, and their incidence is thought to be growing for several years. It is intriguing to do ecological studies using aggregated data, taking into consideration social and economic elements, which are sparse, particularly among adults.

Methods: An ecological cross-sectional observational study was carried out utilizing anonymized and aggregated data from the National Health Survey. The data used are from 1993, 1995, 1997, 2001, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2011, 2014, and 2017 (a 25-year period). Descriptive statistics on the evolution of allergy prevalence were acquired, as well as potential contributing factors (social, demographic, economic, etc.). The statistics comprised measurements of central position (mean, median), dispersion (standard deviation, variance, coefficient of variation), distribution (ranges, maximum and lowest values, skewness and kurtosis), normality tests, significance tests, and multivariate analysis.

Results: The prevalence of allergies in Spain has increased significantly (more than 50%). The growth has been consistent across all age and gender categories, although it has been particularly noticeable among young women. Furthermore, populations with more than 400,000 people have the highest prevalence, as do those with higher incomes and educational levels.

Conclusion: We have quantifiable data that supports the continuing increase of allergies and links it to societal factors (younger individuals, women, higher income and education levels).

Keywords: Allergy, Epidemiology, Prevalence, Multivariate analysis, Social factors, Spain

Introduction

Allergic illnesses are among the most common causes of chronic pathology; their incidence is estimated to have been increasing for years, and they impose an additional and growing load on health-care costs (1-3). Currently, allergy is viewed as a pathology that is expanding rapidly, affecting a large

proportion of the population, and manifesting mostly in developed countries with Western lifestyles (1).

Allergies and related disorders impact nearly 20% of the global population, but the differences across the many places evaluated were significant, and there was no clear regional trend (4). There was significant heterogeneity between nations, with asthma ranging

from 0.9% to 29% and rhinitis ranging from 2.8% to 45.7% (5).

It is also assumed that pollution will have a significant impact. Furthermore, many review publications emphasize the role of climate change and global warming in allergy formation (6,7). They would influence physical parameters like air pressure, rainfall, and environmental temperature, as well as biological factors like plant pollen production. All of this would have an impact on the target organs involved in allergy and asthma pathophysiology (7). However, when we look for quantifiable evidence of all of these assertions, we discover that epidemiological data on allergy and asthma in our nation are quite limited in the general Spanish population (8). Normally, we have unrepresentative samples of groups of patients who went to the allergist with the suspicion of having an allergic disease, by examining the different proportions of allergens that cause allergies and which diagnostic methods and treatments are most commonly used by specialists (9).

Furthermore, there are no ecological studies that use aggregated data (10, 11), and it is worth noting that research on allergy prevalence in relation to social and economic determinants is limited, particularly in the adult population.

To our knowledge, this is the first study to use aggregate data on allergy diagnoses gathered by national institutions. An observational study was conducted over a 25-year period or time series, gathering allergy diagnoses as well as socio-demographic data such as age, gender, population type, educational level, and economic status. Descriptive statistics and multivariate analysis were used, albeit the latter was never applied to the study's subject.

Material and methods

Type of study

An ecological cross-sectional observational study was carried out using primarily anonymized, aggregated data from the National Health Survey, which are available to the public on the Ministry of Health's website (<https://www.mscbs.gob.es>, date of access 1-2-2022 to 1-2-2023) and the National Statistics Institute's website (12-14).

Data sources

Data were collected from the National Health Surveys and the National Statistics Institute. This is a cross-sectional, population-based study. The study population and information sources were based on

data from 1993, 1995, 1997, 2001, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2011, 2014, and 2017 (12-14). These are population-based surveys conducted at home with personal interviews and a standardized questionnaire. The reference population is 16 years or older, not institutionalized, and lives in Spain.

These surveys cover a variety of common topics, including health status, habits or lifestyles, preventive measures, usage of health services, and, in recent editions, the environment. The respondent was asked if they had suffered from an allergy in the previous 12 months, among other ailments, and if they had been diagnosed by a physician. Also, whether you had tried any medications for this ailment.

Data on allergic pathology and its impact on specific disorders were collected:

- gender, age, and type of population
- gender, age range, and educational level
- gender, age group, and socioeconomic status/class

The selected data is from 2017. It was decided to exclude data from Spain's most recent National Health Survey, which was conducted in 2020, because the results (divided into two periods by the pandemic) are not comparable to the historical series, and the indicators reflected behaviors that could have changed as a result of the interviews' situation.

Statistical analysis

First, a descriptive analysis of the qualifying samples was conducted. Using the data sources mentioned in previous sections, as well as the years 1993, 1995, 1997, 2001, 2003, 2006, 2011, 2014, and 2017, we collected information on allergy pathology and its involvement based on certain conditions: gender, age, and population type; gender, age, and level of education; and gender, age, and economic social class. The data was cleaned such that it could be used statistically.

All statistical analyses were conducted with the statistical tool R version 1.4.2 and Microsoft Excel version 16.0 (Microsoft Corporation).

Ross Ihaka and Robert Gentleman (15) invented R, a statistical analysis and graphics system. R is a very flexible programming language oriented for computational statistics, data analysis, and graphics development. We used the following R packages:

- Rcmdr and RcmdrMisc (RCommander)

Statistics, Summaries (numerical summary, normalcy test, correlation test); Means (single-samples t-test,

independent samples t-test, one-way ANOVA), variances (Test F, Bartlett test, Levene test), nonparametric tests, Dimensional analysis and fit models (k-means) Graphs,

- Plot, Biplot, Library Cluster, and Factomines.

The selection of statistical variables, both hygienic (for example, prevalence data, which is the proportion of instances in a population with a specific feature or condition) and non-sanitary (social, demographic, economic, etc.).

These analyses were performed:

1. Descriptive statistics on the progression of allergy prevalence over 25 years. According to age (15-24, 25-44, 35-44, 45-64, 65-74, and over 75 years) and gender.
2. Descriptive statistics on allergy prevalence over time based on population type, age, and gender. By population type (less than 10,000, 10,000-50,000, 50,000-100,000, 100,000-400,000, and more than 400,000).
3. Descriptive statistics on allergy prevalence by level of study (without studies, first grade, second grade 1, second grade 2, and third grade).
4. Descriptive data on allergy prevalence by economic level (I, II, III, IV, V, and VI; I is the greatest and VI is the lowest) (16).

We also carried out the following analyses:

- Descriptive statistics include measurements of central location (mean and median), dispersion (standard deviation, variance, coefficient of variation), and distribution (ranges, maximum and lowest values, skewness, and kurtosis).

- The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to evaluate normality. The Barlett and Levene tests were used to assess homocedasticity. The Student and Welch tests were employed to validate significance.

- Descriptive statistics were converted into tables and graphs:

- Tables comparing prevalence percentages by group (age, gender, population type, education level, and economic status).
- Tables containing summary parameters from descriptive statistics.
- Line representations of time series based on the groupings mentioned.

- Graphs of prevalence percentages comparing groupings (age, gender, population type, education level, and economic status).
- Multivariate representation.

Given the data's complexity and size, we performed multivariate analysis (17). These are statistical methods designed to examine data sets containing numerous measurable variables at the same time. They provide a better grasp of the topic under investigation by acquiring data that univariate and bivariate approaches cannot. Cluster analysis is a multivariate technique that classifies things by constructing groups/clusters that are as homogeneous as feasible within themselves yet heterogeneous with respect to one another.

K-means clustering, a non-jerarquic method, is the most often used unsupervised machine learning technique for partitioning a given data set into k groups (i.e., k clusters), where k indicates the number of groups pre-specified by the analyst. It divides things into numerous groups (clusters) so that objects within the same cluster are as similar as possible (high intra-class similarity), while objects from different clusters are as dissimilar as possible (low inter-class similarity).

In k-means clustering, each cluster is represented by its center (i.e., centroid), which is the average of the points assigned to the cluster. We plot the curve based on the number of clusters k. The optimal number of clusters was determined by the location of a bend (knee) in the plot (this is generally considered as an indicator of the appropriate number of clusters).. The "Elbow method" for computing and determining the appropriate number of clusters to group your data has been combined into a single function (fviz_nbclust). Partitioning methods, such as k-means clustering, need users to define the number of clusters to be formed. (fviz_nbclust) calculates and visualizes the ideal number of clusters using various approaches.

Results

Descriptive statistics on the evolution of allergy prevalence over 25 years

The data were collected from 1993 to 2017, with additional measurements taken in 1993, 1995, 1997, 2001, 2003, 2006, 2011, 2014, and 2017. Table 1 depicts the evolution of allergy prevalence in Spain from 1993 to 2017, both in total and individually in males and females, with age groups and data for each year of measurement. Table 1 demonstrates that the increase in all age and sex groups has been consistent

over the previous 25 years. Furthermore, as Table 1 shows, when we look at the average of the last 25 years in the general population, the increase in allergies is primarily found in younger groups and women.

Figure 1 shows a time-series graph of the average prevalence of allergies from 1993 to 2017. In 1993, 6.25% of persons were diagnosed with allergies by a doctor, which has risen to 15.28% by 2017. The striking aspect is the 59.09% increase in prevalence over 25 years, which is also statistically significant ($P = 2.107 \times 10^{-13}$), as demonstrated by Student's Test calculations for independent samples using the numbers in 1993 and 2017.

Cluster analysis was done using multivariate analyses. This analysis used the k-means and R clusplot algorithms to arrange data into clusters, which are represented graphically in Figure 2. We can observe in which cluster each age and gender niche is grouped (using the mean of each throughout the span of years measured, as shown in Table 1), as well as their specific allergy prevalence figures. The variables are assigned, following the sequence of the numerical key regarding age groups in Table 1, in each of the referred clusters: 4 2 2 4 4 3 3 1 3 2 4 4 1 1 1 1 2 2 2 2 2 2.

Descriptive statistics of the prevalence of allergy with respect to the type of population

If not only age and gender but also the type of population in terms of population size (less than 10,000, between 10,000 and 50,000, between 50,000 and 100,000, between 100,000 and 400,000, and more than 400,000) were taken into account, the evolution of allergy prevalence can be seen in Tables 2 and 3A.

In 2017, men (15.06%) and women (22.06%) had higher allergy rates in communities of more than 400,000 people. When we compare the prevalence difference in 2017 between populations with more than 400,000 inhabitants to the average total figure for all populations (18.66% vs. 15.28%), we find that it is 3.38, signifying 18.11% in favor of the former.

A statistically significant increase ($p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$) was observed between the first (1993) and final (2017) groups using the Student's Test. Similarly, comparing only populations with over 400,000 people regarding the means (Table 3A) of the female and male groups, we notice that the rise in 25 years is similarly significant ($p < 1.68 \times 10^{-12}$ and $p < 1.8 \times 10^{-14}$).

Table 3 ABC shows a centered distribution with the median following values similar to the mean, which is supported by both the kurtosis and skewness coefficients. The kurtosis is mainly substantially negative, while the skewness coefficient is generally

somewhat positive. The sample dispersion by standard deviation is around 20% in most groups. The Shapiro-Wilk normality test confirms a normal distribution.

Descriptive statistics of the prevalence of allergy according to level of education

If the levels of studies considered as such: no studies, first degree, second degree first cycle, second degree second cycle, and third degree were taken into account; it can be seen in Figure 3 and Table 3B that the values of allergy are higher in people with higher levels, both in total and when separated by gender.

Descriptive statistics of the prevalence of allergy according to economic level

To characterize the economic level, we used the occupational social class, which obtains the social class of the individual who works or has worked, as well as the main breadwinner, and selects the most privileged of these two, grouping into social classes I, II, and III (more privileged) and IV, V, and VI (less privileged) according to that adapted for the National Health Survey (16).

The quantitative data in Table 3C show that greater income levels are associated with higher levels of allergy than lower income levels. There is a two-point gap between the allergy level VI and the predominance of high levels.

Discussion

It is well acknowledged that there is little contemporary data on allergy and related atopic diseases in adults. Although the evidence on the true prevalence of allergy is confounded by a lack of data, it was decided that there is a real increase in allergy in adults, which represents a serious global public health issue. To improve disease prevention outcomes, educational activities should be addressed on patients and their families. Public health officials should advocate for enough resources for the diagnosis, control, treatment, and prevention of allergic disorders (1,3).

The results to be highlighted are, first, evidence that the increase in allergy prevalence in Spain (over 25 years) is quite large (59.09%). The growth has been consistent over time across all age and gender groups, but it has been particularly noticeable among young people and women. Furthermore, the greatest statistics correspond to the group of persons with the highest education and income levels.

Figure 1. Time series of allergy prevalence average from 1993 to 2017. The percentage prevalence is expressed in ordinates and in abscissas for each of the years in which the surveys were carried out. Prevalence is also expressed numerical.

CLUSTERS

1

2

4

3

Figure 2. Graphical representation of the clusters into which the 25-year allergy distribution is divided by age and gender. Using the k-means and R clusplot algorithms, we obtain a grouping in clusters and their graphical representation. The variables are assigned, following the order of the numerical key, in each of the clusters referred to below. Clustering vector: 4 2 2 4 4 3 3 1 3 2 4 4 1 1 1 1 2 2 2 2 2 2 4 3. The clusters are selected by highest prevalence and lowest prevalence. The conglomerates that have few components: number 3, 4 and 1, It would correspond to the lowest prevalence. The most numerous which is cluster 2 comprises the highest prevalence.

Table 1. Classification of the evolution of the prevalence of allergy in Spain from 1993 to 2017, both by total figures for both genders, and separately in males and females, adding the age groups and showing the data for each of the years

	Age (Year)	1993	1995	1997	2001	2003	2006	2011	2014	2017	Average
Both genders	Total	6,25	8,05	7,95	8,03	9,83	10,54	10,74	13,37	15,28	10,00
	15-24	7,95	11,79	10,66	10,63	13,55	13,82	13,20	13,80	19,05	12,72
	25-34	6,41	8,69	7,97	7,98	11,89	12,24	12,16	16,95	17,86	11,35
	35-44	5,99	5,47	6,97	7,50	8,85	11,41	11,92	15,28	16,37	9,97
	45-54	5,46	7,18	6,90	8,05	8,70	8,85	10,18	13,55	14,64	9,28
	55-64	5,98	7,01	7,06	7,66	8,64	9,79	9,60	12,01	14,04	9,09
	65-74	5,16	7,64	7,11	7,35	8,01	7,57	9,04	10,53	12,74	8,35
	75 & more	5,34	6,08	6,91	5,61	7,06	7,70	7,33	8,24	11,44	7,30
Men	Total	5,32	6,83	6,18	6,63	8,72	8,91	9,66	11,25	13,23	8,53
	15-24	7,61	11,78	9,25	10,83	14,35	13,33	13,52	12,99	18,97	12,51
	25-34	5,79	8,19	7,27	7,93	11,49	11,20	11,93	14,03	14,84	10,30
	35-44	4,70	3,89	4,72	5,24	8,42	9,44	11,35	13,19	15,88	8,54
	45-54	3,64	4,93	4,44	5,51	6,32	6,19	7,94	11,09	12,62	6,96
	55-64	4,71	5,37	4,71	4,69	6,14	7,25	7,02	9,71	10,51	6,68
	65-74	3,64	5,34	4,18	4,90	4,88	5,73	7,03	7,19	9,52	5,82
	75 & more	5,17	2,94	5,20	4,62	4,44	5,82	5,70	6,63	7,33	5,32
Women	Total	7,14	9,19	9,60	9,34	10,90	12,10	11,77	15,38	17,22	11,40
	15-24	8,33	11,80	12,20	10,43	12,73	14,34	12,86	14,65	19,14	12,94
	25-34	7,07	9,20	8,66	8,03	12,30	13,36	12,39	19,88	20,86	12,42
	35-44	7,32	7,00	9,22	9,72	9,28	13,45	12,52	17,45	16,86	11,42
	45-54	7,26	9,23	9,20	10,52	11,06	11,48	12,39	16,00	16,66	11,53
	55-64	7,19	8,55	9,21	10,40	10,99	12,18	12,05	14,21	17,42	11,36
	65-74	6,40	9,11	9,13	9,13	10,48	9,00	10,78	13,47	15,65	10,35
	75 & more	5,43	8,65	8,26	6,37	8,84	9,04	8,40	9,30	14,16	8,72

Table 2. Classification of the evolution of the prevalence of allergy in Spain from 1993 to 2017 respect to the type of population (number of inhabitants, both by total figures for both sexes, and separately in males and females, showing the data for each of the years of measurement

Both genders						Men						Women					
A	B	C	D	E	F	A	B	C	D	E	F	A	B	C	D	E	F
1993	6,25	5,00	5,47	6,84	6,58	9,33	5,32	4,32	4,64	6,05	5,69	7,52	7,14	5,67	6,31	7,61	7,42
1995	8,05	6,46	6,17	9,00	9,18	10,53	6,83	7,20	4,72	7,72	7,21	8,09	9,19	5,80	7,56	10,19	10,98
1997	7,95	6,19	7,19	8,20	7,91	11,02	6,18	4,86	6,06	3,15	6,01	9,56	9,60	7,44	8,29	13,18	9,63
2001	8,03	7,06	8,33	8,82	8,03	8,52	6,63	5,10	7,54	8,19	6,71	6,51	9,34	8,90	9,08	9,40	9,26
2003	9,83	10,27	9,40	10,65	10,02	9,13	8,72	8,82	8,78	9,65	8,43	8,28	10,90	11,64	10,00	11,65	11,56
2006	10,54	10,06	10,44	10,54	11,04	10,59	8,91	8,24	8,21	9,10	9,94	9,21	12,10	11,72	12,60	11,89	12,18
2011	10,74	9,91	10,51	10,53	11,83	10,87	9,66	10,69	8,49	10,05	9,07	10,63	11,77	9,10	12,41	11,01	14,42
2014	13,37	12,22	12,99	12,74	13,89	15,06	11,25	10,58	11,32	9,06	12,23	12,43	15,38	13,92	14,61	16,33	15,38
2017	15,28	12,95	15,18	13,36	15,93	18,66	13,23	11,71	13,24	12,03	13,95	15,06	17,22	14,22	17,00	14,63	17,71

A: Until 10,000; B: 10,000-50,000; C: 50,000-100,000; D: 100,000-400,000; E: More than 400,000; F: Total

Figure 3. The average prevalence of allergy in the time series, expressing in ordinates the percentage of prevalence and in abscissas the different groups according to the level of studies and differentiating in total

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of the evolution of the allergy prevalence in the time series, with respect to the type of population

	Standard error	Median	Standard deviation	Variance	Kurtosis Swekness	Both genders	Total
A	Prevalence of allergy : Type of population (inhabitants)						
Average	10,00360699	0,957617717	9,834715973	2,872853151	8,253285225	-0,055062647	0,734136026
Until 10000	8,90094991	0,939461816	9,90593923	2,818385448	7,943296536	-1,477866477	0,05660381
10000 - 50000	9,52048657	1,056766149	9,397414458	3,170298446	10,05079224	-0,32793097	0,536586946
50000 - 100000	10,07790243	0,700601484	10,53368425	2,101804451	4,41758195	-0,557558221	0,191768136
100000- 400000	10,49122569	1,008635448	10,0206386	3,025906344	9,156109205	-0,314753746	0,631658436
> 400000	11,52357946	1,090625755	10,59202431	3,271877265	10,70518084	2,195552548	1,627204762
B	Prevalence of allergy : Education level						
Average	12,48072235	1,132773295	12,05434841	2,26554659	5,132701352	-2,726219294	0,571916953
No study	10,84226818	1,104659402	10,57490641	2,209318804	4,881089579	0,405467038	0,640231966
First level	10,87669876	1,028443862	10,30412113	2,056887725	4,230787111	0,318458398	1,147336251
Second level 1	12,08359768	1,036171528	12,43066538	2,072343055	4,294605739	-3,299127334	-0,467144806
Second level 2	13,30093438	1,29642568	13,30532053	2,59285136	6,722878175	-2,497951672	-0,006935542
Third level	14,71079014	1,169113951	14,36239719	2,338227902	5,467309721	-0,07055105	0,734867498
C	Prevalence of allergy : Economic level						
I	11,29798587	1,06164073	10,6402992	2,600478094	6,762486316	-0,310821945	0,566454187
II	12,78639394	1,07237783	12,19983563	2,626778495	6,899965264	-0,786776463	0,541410661
III	13,08556166	1,46659094	13,29558763	3,592399467	12,90533393	0,582825795	-0,609606251
IV	11,51480028	0,95035666	11,3414161	2,327888891	5,419066688	-1,221874836	0,217873728
V	11,18399688	1,29682066	9,938984465	3,176548923	10,09046306	0,293853682	1,042162612
VI	10,24586211	0,971357831	9,599767711	2,379331043	5,661216211	-1,147669067	0,687773252

In all of the groups included in Table 1, the increase has been consistent over time, and by 2017, the prevalence figures in all niches by age and gender are much greater than in prior years. The assumption that allergies have increased unstoppably in recent years has always existed and has been tacitly recognized, but it is evident that we now have quantitative data to back up this claim. The figure for men has increased from 5.32% to 13.23%, and for women from 7.14% to 17.22%. The 15-24 age group consistently outperforms the other age groups.

When both sexes are considered, the percentage increases from 7.95% to 19.05%. Also remarkable is the group of 25-34 year-old women, who had the biggest peak of all figures in 2017, at 20.86%, up from 7.07% in 1993. The prevalence draws from the youngest to the oldest groups, like a stairway that gradually descends to the older age groups. In 2017, as in previous years, the picture is similar, with the exception of 2014, when the 25-34 age group was slightly higher. In addition, the 25-34 age group is likewise the second most affected, and it does so consistently across all years. In women, the 15-24 age group is no longer dominant, having been eclipsed in 2014 and 2017 by the 25-34 decade.

It is well known that a small number of research with diverse techniques or insufficient data make determining allergy prevalence problematic. One study of allergy epidemiology conducted in Spain, which is more similar to ours in technique, acknowledged that allergic disorders have increased in recent decades (18). It should also be emphasized that there are very few allergy prevalence studies in the broader Spanish population. More than 21.5% of the participants in the study reported having an allergy. The prevalence was higher in women (24.6%), the 18-24 age group (26.9%), and populations larger than 500,000 (24.3%). We can see that the prevalence figure in our situation is high, albeit smaller than in the aforementioned study, but there are similarities with female preponderance and young age groups, as well as a higher proportion in densely populated areas.

When our data is compared to international studies, Phase I of the Global Asthma Network (a multinational cross-sectional population study using the same basic methodology as the International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Phase III Childhood) reported 14.4% allergic rhinitis, which is comparable to our data. There was a correlation between increased frequency in women and the rise of allergies in all population categories (18).

Unlike adults, there is worry about the global prevalence of pediatric allergy diseases. The International Study of Asthma and Allergy in Childhood (ISAAC phase III) found a modest global

increase in the prevalence of rhinitis, but the variances were substantial among the areas evaluated, and there was no consistent regional pattern (19-21). According to studies conducted by the International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC), the prevalence of allergic rhinitis in Spain was 8.5% between the ages of six and seven and 16.3% between the ages of thirteen and fourteen (5). Table 3 shows the evolution of allergy prevalence when age and gender are taken into account, as well as the kind of population in terms of population size. Except for 2003, 2006, and 2011, the subsequent years have the highest population of over 400,000. In 2017, there was an increase in allergies among men (15.06%) and women (22.06%) in populations with over 400,000 residents. This is still true in 2014, but to a lesser extent. In 2011, the maximum was seen in groups ranging from 100,000 to 400,000 people (11.83% for both sexes and 14.42% for women), but to a lower extent. In 2006, there were no significant disparities between population types. It is assumed that the rising prevalence of respiratory diseases in recent years can be attributed to a variety of environmental changes, including increased levels of chemicals (particulate matter and gaseous components such as nitrogen dioxide and ozone) and biological triggers (aeroallergens). Several papers highlight this. In our case, there is an increase in allergy in populations of more than 400,000 inhabitants, where higher pollution is assumed; however, when we compare it to the global increase in allergy, regardless of population type, which has been more than 50%, we may conclude that it is due to other factors, such as the fact that younger age groups, which have a higher proportion of allergy, are more prevalent in large cities.

On the other hand, our findings, which suggest an increase in allergies at high education and economic levels, vary from those of other writers who have investigated the association between economic status and rhinitis (21-23). Their findings in the child population indicate that increased economic status reduces the risk of allergy, implying that economically disadvantaged groups are more likely to be exposed to environmental risk factors, which may increase susceptibility to the development of allergic respiratory diseases (21, 22). Furthermore, education is regarded as a reliable predictor of social and economic status, and educational levels are utilized to study their association with allergy.

A 2006 study looked into whether low parental education has a direct effect on allergy in children, but no direct or indirect effects were discovered (23). A systematic review would partially accord with our findings, as the bulk of publications show a link between allergies and high socioeconomic level (24).

As a result of national health surveys, we were unable to locate any publications that investigated the association between adult allergies and socioeconomic characteristics (such as educational level, social class, or income level) in the general population. It would be fascinating to compare our findings to those of other national health surveys from different nations. Although there are no epidemiological research on the entire population, we did find studies on certain demographic groups, such as military-age males (25) or schoolchildren of various levels and university students (26).

Allergies and other atopic illnesses have developed dramatically in recent decades (1). Furthermore, the most notable research found wide differences among the many places evaluated, with no uniform regional pattern (5, 19, 20). However, when we look for quantifiable evidence of all of these claims, we discover that epidemiological data on allergy and asthma in the general population are extremely uncommon, and there are no ecological studies that consider aggregated data. Furthermore, only a few research provided a complete overview of the socioeconomic impacts of atopic disorders, and these economic studies demonstrated a wide range of applicable methodologies and conclusions.

Among the few studies we discovered on the subject, a systematic analysis of prior publications that link allergy disease to socioeconomic factors stands out (24). The significance of socioeconomic status in the development of asthma and allergies is unclear, with some studies indicating to lower risks and others pointing to higher risks. Their conclusion is similar to ours: evidence from this systematic analysis implies that asthma is related with lower socioeconomic status, whereas allergies are associated with better socioeconomic status (24). Throughout the 1990s, there was increased attention in the role of environmental variables in asthma and allergies (6). It is assumed that the recent increase in the frequency of respiratory diseases can be attributed to a variety of environmental changes, including an increase in the presence of chemicals (particulate matter and gaseous components such as nitrogen dioxide and ozone) and biological triggers (aeroallergens) (6, 7).

Despite inconsistent facts, there is a widespread belief that climate change alters the production and dispersion of chemical and biological components of air pollution. Several articles highlight this (6, 7). It increases the allergenic concentration of pollen and spores in the atmosphere, which has a proinflammatory effect on allergic patients' airways. Furthermore, it is widely assumed that pollution-modified aeroallergens are more capable of stimulating airway reactivity in allergic subjects, resulting in bronchial asthma symptoms, based on the

broad notion that increased pollution and global warming cause a rise in allergy and asthma (7). In our case, there is an increase in allergy in populations of more than 400,000 inhabitants, where higher pollution is assumed; however, when we compare it to the global increase in allergy, regardless of population type, which has been more than 50%, we may conclude that it is due to other factors, such as the fact that younger age groups, which have a higher proportion of allergy, are more prevalent in large cities.

Conclusion

We have quantitative data from a 25-year series that support the relentless growth (more than 50%) in allergy prevalence in Spain and link it to social determinants (younger individuals, women, higher income and education levels).

References

1. Platts-Mills, T.A. The allergy epidemics: 1870–2010. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2015;136 (1):3–13.
2. Ojeda, P., Sanz de Burgoa, V. Costs associated with workdays lost and utilization of health care resources because of asthma in daily clinical practice in Spain. *J Investig Allergol Clin Immunol* 2013;23 (4): 234-241.
3. Dierick, B.J.H., Van der Molen, T., Flokstra-de Blok, B.M.J., Muraro, A., Postma, M.J., Kocks, J.W.H. et al. Burden and socioeconomics of asthma, allergic rhinitis, atopic dermatitis and food allergy. *Expert Rev Pharmacoeconom Outcomes Res* 2020;20:5: 437-453.
4. Bauchau, V. Prevalence and rate of diagnosis of allergic rhinitis in Europe. *Eur Respir J* 2004;24(5):758–764.
5. Ait-Khaled, N., Pearce, N., Anderson, H.R., Ellwood, P., Montefort, S., Shah, J.; ISAAC Phase Three Study Group. Global map of the prevalence of symptoms of rhinoconjunctivitis in children: The International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC) Phase Three. *Allergy* 2009; 64: 123-148.
6. Weiland, S.K., Hüsing, A., Strachan, D., Rzehak, P., Pearce, N.; ISAAC Phase One Study Group. Climate and the prevalence of symptoms of asthma, allergic rhinitis and atopic eczema in children. *Occup Environ Med* 2004; 61(7): 609-615.
7. D'Amato, G., Pawankar, R., Vitale, C., Lanza, M., Molino, A., Stanziola, A., et al. Climate change and air pollution: effects on respiratory allergy. *Allergy Asthma Immunol Res* 2016;8(5):391-395.

8. Gaig, P., García Abujeta, J.L., Muñoz-Lejarazu, D., Leonart Bellfill, R., Caballero, T. [Prevalencia de alergia en la población adulta Española]. Spanish. *Alergol Inmunol Clin* 2004; 19(2):68-74.
9. Ojeda, P., Sastre, J., Olaguibel, J.M., Chivato, T. *Alergológica 2015: A National Survey on Allergic Diseases in the Adult Spanish Population*. *J Investig Allergolog Clin Immunolog* 2018, 28(3):151-164
10. Morgenstern, H. Ecologic studies in epidemiology: Concepts, principle, and methods. *Annu Rev Public Health* 1995;16:61-81.
11. Black, N. Why we need observational studies to evaluate the effectiveness of health care. *BMJ* 1996; 312(7040):1215-1218.
12. Ministerio de Sanidad y Política Social. [Encuesta Nacional de Salud de España]. Spanish. Available from: <http://www.msps.es/estadEstudios/estadisticas/encuestaNacional/ense.htm>.
13. Ministerio de Sanidad y Política Social. [Encuesta Nacional de Salud de España]. Spanish. Available from: <http://www.msps.es/estadEstudios/encuestaNacional/añosanteriores.htm>.
14. Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE). Available from: <http://ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/es>.
15. Ihaka, R., Gentleman, R. R: a language for data analysis and graphics. *J Comput Graph Stat* 1996; 5(3): 299–314.
16. Alonso, J., Pérez, P., Sáez, M., Murillo, C. [Validez de la ocupación como indicador de la clase según la clasificación del Registro General Británico]. Spanish. *Gac Sanit* 1997;11(5):205-213.
17. Bilodeau, M., Brenner, D. *Theory of multivariate statistics*. Springer New York; 1999. <https://doi.org/10.1007/b97615>.
18. Mortimer, K., Lesosky, M., García-Marcos, L., Asher, M.I., Pearce, N., Ellwood, E., et al. Global Asthma Network Phase I Study Group. The burden of asthma, hay fever and eczema in adults in 17 countries: GAN Phase I study. *Eur Respir J* 2022;60(3):2102865.
19. Asher, M.I., Weiland, S.K., ISAAC Steering Committee. The International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC). *Clin Exp Allergy* 1998;28(Suppl 5):52-66.
20. Strachan, D., Sibbald, B., Weiland, S., Ait-Khaled, N., Anabwani, G., Anderson, H.R., et al. Worldwide Variations in prevalence of symptoms of allergic rhinoconjunctivitis in children: The International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC). *Pediatr Allergy Immunol* 1997;8(4):161-176.
21. Linneberg, A. Burden of allergic respiratory disease: A systematic review. *Clin Mol Allergy* 2016; 14:12. 34.
22. Almqvist, C., Pershagen, G., Wickman, M. Low socioeconomic status as a risk factor for asthma, rhinitis and sensitization at 4 years in a birth cohort. *Clin Exp Allergy* 2005;35(5):612-618.
23. Rocco, I., Cilluffo, G., Ferrante, G., Cibella, F., Marcon, A., Marchetti, P., et al. Investigating the relationship between parental education, asthma and rhinitis in children using path analysis. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 2022;19 (21):14551.
24. Uphoff, E., Cabieses, B., Pinart, M., Valdés, M., Antó, J.M., Wright, J. A systematic review of socioeconomic position in relation to asthma and allergic diseases. *Eur Respir J* 2015; 46(2): 364–374.
25. Bråbäck, L., Hjern, A., Rasmussen, F. Social class in asthma and allergic rhinitis: a national cohort study over three decades. *Eur Respir J* 2005;26:1064–1068.
26. Eagan, T.M.L., Gulsvik, A., Eidec, G.E., Bakke, P.S. The effect of educational level on the incidence of asthma and respiratory symptoms. *Respir Med* 2004;98:730–736.